

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 2

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil **IQTISODIYOT** va **TARAQQIYOT**

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Elektron nashr. 598 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 29-fevralda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

MUNDARIJA

Ilm-fanga baxshida umr Baxtiyor Islamov	8
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda “yashil” iqtisodiyotni keng tatbiq qilishning ahamiyati Gulnora Abdurahmonova Kalandarovna, Sanjar Baxodirovich G’oipnazarov	10
Brand Capital as a Determinant of Institutional Prestige and Student Choice in the Higher Education System ... Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna	16
Inson va atrof-muhit dialektikasi: nomutanosiblik ko’rsatkichlari va ekologik muammolar Butaboyev Maxammadjon Tuychiyevich, Maxmudov Nosir Maxmudovich	24
Yashil budjetlashtirish va uni O‘zbekistonda joriy etish istiqbollari Meylev Obid Raxmatullayevich, Gofurova Kamola Xayrulla qizi	30
Iqtisodiyotda ta’lim va fan integratsiyasining asosiy yo’nalishlari Yormatov Ilmidin Toshmatovich	35
Transport vositalari va yo’llar turizm transport infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning muhim omilidir Agzamov Shaxboz Akmalovich	39
Bank xizmatlarini raqamlashtirish orqali samaradorligini oshirish A. X. Salamov	44
Biznes-reja baliqchilik xo’jaligi rivojlanishi uchun asos sifatida Dosmurotova Shaxista Kengashovna	48
Mamlakatning investitsiyaviy jozibadorligi va uning lizing munosabatlari rivojlanishi bilan bog’liqligi Axmediyeva Aliya Toxtarovna	55
Turizmni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkabilovich	63
Tijorat banklari depozit operatsiyalari samaradorligini oshirish muammolari va ularni bartaraf etish yo’llari Shamsiyev Nodir Muratovich	67
Hududlarni rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning samaradorligini oshirish masalalari Shagazatov Oybek bahodirovich	72
Hududlar biznes muhitini rivojlantirish va samarali boshqarish yo’nalishlari Davlatov Sanjar Abdimannonovich	76
Ijtimoiy rivojlanish xulq-atvor paradigmasida yoshlarning tadbirkorlik faoliyatini tartibga solishning nazariy asoslari Mirzatov Baxtiyor Toxirovich	80
Korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatida raqamli transformatsiyaning muhim yo’nalishlari Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	84
O‘zbekistonda agroturizmni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish (Buxoro viloyati misolida) Yoriyeva Farangiz Murodillayevna	89
Innovatsion tadbirkorlik muhitini kompleks baholashda xalqaro tashkilotlar tajribasi Nazarova Umida Avazovna	94
Turizm faoliyatini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish samaradorligini oshirishning ayrim usullari Mirzaxodjayev Alisher Botirovich	98
Globalashuv sharoitida transchegaraviy suv resurslardan samarali foydalanishni boshqirish Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich	103
Surxondaro viloyati iqtisodiyotida kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning o’rni va ahamiyati Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	108
Ta’lim muassasalarida xarajatlarni moliyaviy nazorat etishning samaradorligi tahlili Eshonqulov Davlatjon Rajabboyevich	113
Ta’minot zanjirini boshqarishda transport logistikasi usullarini takomillashtirish Zoxidova Nazokat Berdimurot qizi	119
Blokcheyn texnologiyasida xavfsizlik masalalari Mamadiyarov Zokir Toshtemirovich	123
Развитие цифровой трансформации банковского сектора Республики Узбекистан Абдурахманова Матлуба Махамдаминовна	129

Asosiy fondlarni hisoblash va baholash usullarini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	135
Rixsimbayev Odiljon Qobiljonovich	
Marketingda tovar harakati tizimini optimallashtirish va modellashtirish	141
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev, Kamola Abdujabborovna Pardayeva	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish uchun strategik taqsimlash strategiyalari: Investitsion Fond Portfellarning qiyosiy tahlili.....	148
Sultonboeva Munira bahodirovna	
Soliq munosabatlarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati: ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar.....	154
Axrorov Zarif Oripovich, Saidmurodov Feruz Sodiqjon o'g'li	
Взаимосвязь инвестиционной стратегии с оценкой эффективности инвестиционного проекта	159
С. С. Алиева, А. Назаров	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarning faoliyati va boshqaruv mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	167
Sheraliyeva Saida Azatovna	
Xizmat safari xarajatlari hisobining huquqiy asoslari	170
Ergashev Sarvar Xudoynazarovich	
Инклюзивное образование и его особенности.....	175
Зайнутдинова Умида Джалоловна	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulk va yer soliqlarini hisoblash va undirish samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	179
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullayevich	
Mamlakatda soliq qarzdorligi vujudga kelishining asosiy sabablari va ularni qisqartirish yo'llari.....	184
Hakimov Ulug'bek Furqat o'g'li	
Mulk qiymatini baholash tushunchasi, baholash obyektlari, baholanadigan qiymat turlari.....	188
Izbosarov Boburjon Bahriddinovich, Yoqubboyev Ilhomjon G'ulomjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta xizmatlarining zamonaviy transformatsiyasi.....	193
G. Adilova	
Biznes subyektlarida samaradorlik masalalarini o'yinlar nazariyasi usuli bilan baholash.....	197
Mardiyev Nurali	
Yengil sanoatda "lean production" konsepsiyasini tatbiq etishning amaliy jihatlari.....	203
Yaxyayeva Inobat Karimovna	
Soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari va ularning tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatiga ta'siri tahlili	207
Borotov Sharofiddin Jumaqul o'g'li	
Ko'chmas mulk bozorini baholashning institutsional asoslari	213
Ishonqulov Nizamjon Fayzullayevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida turizm xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	221
Amriyeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
O'zbekistonning bank-moliya tizimi hamda unda Islom moliyasi instrumentlarini jalb etishdagi joriy tendensiyalar	226
Eshimov Alisher Dasmurodovich	
Tashqi savdoda notarif usullarni qo'llashning iqtisodiy oqibatlarini aniqlash metodologiyasi (rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi).....	234
Norqobilov Akobir Iso o'g'li	
Reklama xizmatlari va uning subyektlar samaradorligini oshirishdagi imkoniyatlari.....	240
Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloyevich	
Ijtimoiy siyosatni amalga oshirishda sog'liqni saqlash tizimini moliyalashtirish asoslari	245
Imonqulov Nuriddin Qo'shmon o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari biznes ekotizimini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	250
Shoymardonov Orziqul Jo'ra o'g'li	
Majburiy tibbiy sug'urtaning vujudga kelishi va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	256
Kenjayev Soxib Sayfiyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida zamonaviy soliq ma'murchiligini joriy etish orqali budjet-soliq siyosati samaradorligini yanada oshirish.....	260
Yuldasheva Shaxnoza Xojiakbar qizi	
Jahon iqtisodiyotining barqaror rivojlanishida derivativlar bozorining roli	266
Shokirov Mirkamol Mirolim o'g'li	
Boshqaruv hisobida mas'uliyat markazlarini tashkil etish masalalari.....	274
Sobirov Otabek Olimjonovich	

Davlat moliyasini boshqarishda moliyaviy nazorat usullaridan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	277
Kultayev Farxod Shavkatovich	
Tijorat banklari foydasi va rentabilik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlilini takomillashtirish	281
Normo'minov Temurbek Sheraliyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida tijorat banklari aktivlar sifatini oshirish yo'llari	284
To'ychiyev Otabek Shamshiyevich	
Venchur kapitalining mohiyati va O'zbekistonda venchur tizimini rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	288
Tadjibayeva Nigora Gulomjonovna	
Innovatsiyalar: zamonaviy iqtisodiyot uchun innovatsion faoliyatni qo'llab-quvvatlash zarurati.....	293
Malikova Dilrabo Muminovna, Tursunov Jahongir Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Budjet daromadlarining shakllanishida egri soliqlarning ta'sirini ko'p omilli ekonometrik modellashtirishda tahlil qilish.....	297
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish yo'llari	302
Abdullayev Boburjon Akbaraliyevich	
Barcha tadbirkorlik subyektlariga teng raqobat sharoitini yaratishda soliq imtiyozlarining o'rni	306
Akbarov Akmalxon Akrom o'g'li	
Hisob siyosati va unda biologik aktivlar hisobini yoritib berish tartibini takomillashtirish	310
Mirzayeva Nargiza Batirovna	
Talabalarning oilali bo'lishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarga iqtisodiy baholashda yangicha yondashuv.....	314
O. U. Shomurodov, A. A. Suyarov, Z. U. Uroqov, J. S. Urazov, A. T. Ablahatov	
Ways to Use the Experience of Foreign Countries in Creating a Beneficial Business Environment for Entrepreneurship And Improving Taxation	319
Mukhlisa Ikramova	
Aholi turmush darajasini oshirishda moliyaviy savodxonlikning o'rni va iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta'siri	325
Yusupov Muhammadali Soxib o'g'li, J.D. Xojiyev	
Temir yo'l sanoat korxonalarida ijtimoiy-mehnat munosabatlarini boshqarish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	329
Kadirova Sharofat Amonovna	
Механизм внедрения аутсорсинговой деятельности в АО “Ўзтемирўйлийловчи”	332
Н. Э. Кахарова	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni yanada rivojlantirish investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	337
Sharipov Bobur Anvar o'g'li	
“STEKLOPLASTIK” MJCHning bozordagi strategik holatini tahlil qilish	342
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Agrar sektorda ekologik toza mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishning nazariy masalalari	348
M. Sh. Nazarova, Z. S. Kazakova	
Methodological Foundations of Bank Lending and Classification of Factors Affecting the Features of Obtaining Loans.....	353
Raxmanova Laylo bahodirovna, A. Karimova	
Agrosanoat klasterlarda tovar-moddiy zaxiralarni samaradorligini KPI orqali baholash uslubiyati	357
Toshpo'latov Azizbek Shermuxamadovich	
Faol tadbirkorlar faoliyatida kambag'al oilalarni iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy holatini yaxshilash imkoniyatlari.....	362
Salamov Ibrohim, Nazarova Maryam Sharifovna, Kazakova Zulayxo Saloxiddinovna, Jonibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna, Xamdamaova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Xudayberdiyeva Ma'rifat Umarovna	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar strategiyasi tahlilining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	369
Tursunova Shaxnoza Farxod qizi	
Процессы цифровизации АО “Hududgazta'minot”	373
Хусанов Кахрамон Нишонович	
O'zbekistonda aholi turmush darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	378
Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna, Eldorbekov G'ofurbek Iskandarbek o'g'li	
Aholi farovonligini oshirishda tadbirkorlik subyektlari uchun kredit tizimini takomillashtirish mexanizmi.....	381
Bobayev Isroiljon Abdinabiyevich	
Mamlakatga jalb qilingan xorijiy kapitalning tovarlar va xizmatlar importi salohiyatiga ta'sirini ekonometrik modellar bilan baholash.....	386
Saydullayev Azamat Jo'raqul o'g'li	

O'zbekistonda bank xizmatlari raqobatbardoshligini baholash mazmuni va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	394
Sh. Madraimov	
Kapital bozorida sug'urta kompaniyalar institutsional investor sifatida	397
Xasanova Lola Mamasharifovna	
Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasida institutsional islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirish va ko'p funksiyali raqamlashtirishning ilmiy asoslari	400
B. B. Berkinov	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi tijorat banklari orqali jinoiy yo'l bilan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirish mexanizmlari.....	409
G'afurov Umidjon Bahodir o'g'li	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda keksa fuqarolarning bandligini oshirish kam ta'minlangan aholi qatlamini qo'llab-quvvatlash usuli sifatida (Yaponiya tajribasi misolida).....	413
Karimov Bekzodjon Iloxovich	
Tashqi savdoni oshirishda boj-tarif siyosatini takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	420
Pardayev Ilhomjon G'ulomjon o'g'li	
Финансы или корпоративные финансы	426
Уринов Бобур Насиллоевич	
In Ensuring Economic Development in the Country Green Economy and its Features	432
Akhunova Shakhistakhon Nomonjanovna, Abdusattorova Mokhirabonu Abdugoppor kizi	
Tijorat banklarining investitsiya faoliyatini rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	437
Jo'rayev O'ktam Panji o'g'li	
Сокращение уровня бедности в Узбекистане.....	443
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
Paxtachilik sohasida ishlab chiqarish jarayonlari samaradorligini oshirishning innovatsion yechimlari va uning foydaga ta'sirini baholash	448
S. B. Inoyatov	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlar bilan ishlash amaliyotidagi muammolar va ularni barataraf etish yo'llari	453
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o'g'li	
Mahalliy budjet daromadlarining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari.....	460
O'lokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish – aholi turmush farovonligini ta'minlashning muhim omili	463
Usmanov Baxodir Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli marketingni rivojlantirish zaruriyati	469
Xalmuxamedova Zebaxon Babaxanovna	
Tijorat banklari o'rtasidagi raqobatni rivojlantirish orqali fond bozorida aksiyalar narxini barqarorligini ta'minlash istiqbollari	473
M. Yuldosheva	
Konchilik sanoati korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirish mexanizmlarining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	480
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
O'zbekistonda banklar moliyaviy xizmatlari va ular sifatining amaldagi holati tahlili	487
Mirzayev Mirza Abdullayevich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining iqtisodiy samaradorlikning raqobatbardoshligini institutsional tahlil qilish mexanizmi.....	492
Saydullayeva Saodat Abdumajidovna	
Integratsiya sharoitida to'qimachilik sanoatining rivojlanishi	499
Ziyayeva Muhtasar Mansurdjanovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini tashkil etish va o'tkazish jarayonlarini takomillashtirish	503
Karamatova Noiba Husnitdinovna	
Davlatning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning nazariy jihatlari	510
Mamatov Mamajan Axmadjonovich	
Экономическое сознание и экономическое мышление: теоретический анализ.....	517
Пардаев Мамаюнус Каршибаевич, Мухаммедов Мурод Мухаммедович	
O'zbekiston respublikasi tijorat banklari tomonidan qurilish korxonalarini kreditlashni takomillashtirish yo'llari	522
Sultanov Baxram Begdullayevich	

Роль искусственного интеллекта в современных технологиях медиаобразования в высших учебных заведениях.....	526
Самигова Гуландом Абдужаббаровна	
Talabalarga moliyaviy yordam dasturlari va ularning ta'lim sifatiga ta'siri	534
Mirzayeva Muhlisa Ubaydullo qizi	
Mintaqaviy investitsion jozibadorlik va investitsion siyosat: nazariy talqin	539
Muminov Akmal Tulkunovich	
Mamlakatni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotida oliy ta'lim tizimining ta'siri	543
Nasimov Adiz Azamat o'g'li, Baxtiyorova Jasmira Jasurovna, Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Respublikada fermer xo'jaliklarga xizmat ko'rsatishni rivojlantirish va agroxizmatlar bozorini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash imkoniyatlari	548
Shukurov Iloxom Safarboyevich	
Turli mamlakatlarda oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirish yo'llari	555
Umarova Moxigul Maxmayunus qizi	
Dehqonchilikni innovatsion asosda rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribasi.....	560
Yuldashev G'iyos Turabekovich	
Tijorat bank xizmat turlarini islomiy bank xizmatlari orqali rivojlantirish istiqbollari	564
Bayjanova Gozsal Sarsengaliyevna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotini baholash va hisobga olishning uslubiy jihatlarini takomillashtirish	570
Boltayev Abror Sayitmuradovich	
Секреты интересного урока в начальной школе.....	577
Гараева Олеся Владимировна	
Iqtisodiyotni barqaror rivojlanishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'rni.....	580
Ibragimova Gulchehra Toxirovna	
Mahsulot va xizmatlarni raqamli transformatsiyasini amalga oshirish algoritmi.....	584
Kucharov Abrorjon Sobirjanovich, Bobojonov Azizjon Babaxanovich, Abdurakhmonov Abdumalik Abdurashidovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining soliq tizimi mamlakatda yashirin iqtisodiyot ulushini qisqartirish vositasi sifatida.....	591
Nabiyev Feruz Nurmurodovich	

IN ENSURING ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE COUNTRY GREEN ECONOMY AND ITS FEATURES

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Abstract: The article considers the important tasks of the transition to a modern “green” economy for the further development of the country’s economy as well as increasing its efficiency, achieving decarbonization and more rational use of natural resources as an important issue. As a result of concern about the environment in different parts of the world, several concepts such as sustainable development, green growth are emerging. It involves different interpretations of the balance between the ecological, social and economic aspects of our society by different sectors.

Key words: green economy, sustainable development, economic stability, social stability, environmental sustainability, concept, sustainable competitiveness, resource efficiency, resource efficiency index, resource consumption.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mamlakat iqtisodiyotini yanada rivojlantirish va uning samaradorligini oshirish hamda tabiiy resurslardan oqilona foydalanishga erishish uchun zamonaviy “yashil” iqtisodiyotga o’tish muhim masala sifatida ko’rib chiqilgan. Dunyoning turli burchaklaridagi atrof-muhit haqida tashvishlanish natijasida barqaror rivojlanish, yashil o’sish kabi bir qancha tushunchalar paydo bo’lmoqda. Bu turli sohalar bo’yicha jamiyatimizning ekologik, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy jihatlari o’rtasidagi muvozanatni turli xil talqin qilishni o’z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so’zlar: yashil iqtisodiyot, barqaror rivojlanish, iqtisodiy barqarorlik, ijtimoiy barqarorlik, ekologik barqarorlik, konsepsiya, barqaror raqobatbardoshlik, resurslar samaradorligi, resurslar samaradorligi indeksi, resurslarni iste’mol qilish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются важные задачи перехода к современной “зеленой” экономике для дальнейшего развития экономики страны, а также повышения ее эффективности, достижения декарбонизации и более рационального использования природных ресурсов как важного вопроса. В результате заботы об окружающей среде в разных частях мира появляется несколько концепций, таких как устойчивое развитие, зеленый рост. Это предполагает различные интерпретации баланса между экологическими, социальными и экономическими аспектами нашего общества различными секторами.

Ключевые слова: зеленая экономика, устойчивое развитие, экономическая стабильность, социальная стабильность, экологическая устойчивость, концепция, устойчивая конкурентоспособность, ресурсоэффективность, индекс ресурсоэффективности, потребление ресурсов.

INTRODUCTION

Today, along with the countries of the world, intensive work is being carried out on the basis of the important program of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “strategy for the transition to a green economy” in 2019-2030, approved on October 4, 2019 in ensuring sustainable development, energy efficiency in our country on the basis of a ham “green “economy.

The study of sustainable economics and its impact on sustainable development is one of the important and vital topics for most researchers, especially in recent years. A sustainable economy is a mechanism that mainly leads to the improvement and development of human well-being, the reduction of environmental risks. In terms of environmental benefits, it improves climate by reducing pollution. It also plays an important role in ensuring employment and investment opportunities, providing material and human resources and opportunities, eliminating poverty and disparity between poverty and social classes, which in turn retain resources to ensure the future of future generations. It is a long-term strategy for the national economy to overcome crises and achieve economic recovery, since a sustainable economy seeks to provide decent job opportunities for everyone.

REVIEW OF THEMATIC LITERATURE

Heinz, J.. Hendricks, B. in the opinion of green growth it refers to the concept that characterizes the form of economic growth that uses natural resources in a sustainable way. In fact, the term is increasingly used worldwide to provide an alternative concept to classical industrial economic growth, leading to the phenomenon of green economics, a real phenomenon of progress and the concept of environmental security.

Lucretia D. it is a fact that during the period of economic growth, more resources and energy are consumed and more waste that affects the environment is produced. Ideally, obtaining a higher economic value from a limited amount of Natural Resources should provide significantly higher economic growth than national resource utilization percentages. Expressed the opinion that resource efficiency is the ability to save costs and introduce new technologies that are able to regulate the economic processes associated with this topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Scientists associate green growth with the green economy through promising changes in the environmental industry sector. This can be followed by the transformation of the final Technology of Environmental Protection into methods of saving resources based on innovations and competitive markets. They pointed out that there is an increasing interest in revising the lifestyle that goes beyond sustainability. At a high level, scientists connect green growth and the green economy with the environmental industry sector through the transition from innovation and competitive market-based environmental protection technology to resource-saving technologies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the most important goals of a sustainable economy is the need to reform policies and regulations. This is the opportunity to hinder a stable economy or create relief. Achieving a sustainable economy requires fundamental changes in the structure and strategies of most companies to achieve sustainable physical and Human Development.

The study sheds light on important aspects, including the concept of a sustainable economy, its importance, goals and levels, the need to move to a sustainable economy as an indicator of the impact of the most important sustainable economy on Sustainable Development, and the most important obstacles to achieving it.

The most important objective of the study is to show the importance of a sustainable economy in sustainable development by optimally spending energy and resources to achieve well-being for all and increase the economic level while keeping the environment free of pollution ^[1].

Often, the following priorities for changing the economy are distinguished in relation to the green economy:

- rational use of Natural Resources, Conservation and restoration of natural capital;
- reduce the intensity of production resources and increase the efficiency of the use of resources and energy;
- expanding the use of renewable energy and the use of low-carbon technologies for fossil fuels;
- improvement of waste recycling system;
- green building expansion;
- development of green transport, transition to low carbon mobility;

- organic farming in agriculture;
- production of environmentally friendly products, including consumer goods;
- formation of responsible behavior of urban residents;
- eradicate poverty, create new jobs and increase social justice.

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) defines a sustainable economy as a mechanism to improve human well-being while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological resource shortages. Simply put, it is an economy that emphasizes the production of less carbon emissions and the placement of all social groups with resources. Aims to reduce pollution and carbon emissions by increasing resource efficiency and energy consumption. A sustainable economy also seeks to grow revenues and jobs that must be made through public and private investment. These investments should be encouraged and supported by targeted government spending, policy reform and change regulations. The development path should preserve and improve natural capital. Indeed, its formation is limited when the need arises, since it is a source of public interest, and is a social issue, especially for the population, whose safety and lifestyle depend on nature.

The most important objective of the study is to show the importance of the green economy in sustainable development by optimally investing energy and resources to promote prosperity and economic level for all, while keeping the environment from pollution.

In contrast to environmental economics or environmental economics, "green economics" is considered to be of a more practical nature. In general, the "green economy" is dominated by real economic policy, areas of concrete activity (energy, innovation, agriculture, etc.) refers to. We can observe this difference in the expression of "green economics" through the words economy (real economic activity) rather than English economics (economic theory or economic sciences such as environmental economics, ecological economics) [2].

The transition to a green economy can be distinguished according to the following grounds:

- the relationship between business administration and the environment;
- methods of managing economic systems that cover environmental and social factors, minimizing environmental damage in the long run due to economic activity;
- the principles of developing new technologies in the field of economic activity and production, directing them to minimize their harm to the environment.

In the implementation of the "green economy", the following principles are important in the selection of methods of scientific cognition and the construction of research strategies:

- the fact that environmental factors are a primary factor in conditions of resource limitation;
- the presence of the need to divide the stages of practical implementation of the green economy into various (theoretical, ideological, political and economic) levels;
- the study clarifies important aspects, including the concept of the green economy, its importance, goals and levels, the most important green jobs, the need to move to the green economy as an indicator of the impact of the green economy on Sustainable Development, and the most important obstacles that hinder sustainable development.
- research on the concept of Green Investment, its importance, motives and its impact on the sustainable environment and the importance of environmental interests in the green economy.

According to the OECD, the economic growth of countries is obtained as the sum of several factors. While some countries provide economic growth at the expense of labor capital and capital generated, the rest can also influence the growth rate by increasing the productivity of natural capital consumption.

A common concept of a "green" economy is a low-carbon economy. The goal of low-carbon development is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere. According to the opinions of many foreign scientists, this reduction in greenhouse gas emissions will lead to the stabilization of the global climate system. One way to achieve this goal is to increase the efficiency of using energy. The main source of CO₂ emissions is the use of coal, oil, gas to be extracted. Currently, most countries and international corporations are reducing pollution from coal, which is an important source of greenhouse gas emissions.

The problem of social justice "sustainable development and equality of opportunity: a better future for all", as shown in the UN global Human Development Report, has many aspects: equality between generations and within generations, between rich and poor countries, compliance with justice in the distribution of income within

individual countries. In particular, it is a difficult issue to overcome the growing gap between rich and poor countries. At the beginning of the 21st century, the wealthiest 20% of the world's population accounted for 86% of consumer spending, while the poorest 20% accounted for 1.5% of spending [4].

Since conventional energy was previously widely used in comparison with renewable energy, fossil energy better complements people's needs. With the expansion of renewable energy consumption, the proportion of fossil energy consumption decreased. If the share of fossil energy consumption is reduced to a certain level, renewable energy at this time will be able to reduce pollution emissions, and its impact on productivity may not be observed, and thus the process of green economic development will also continue.

Figure 1: World Energy Resources stakes (1800-2022) [3]

The main consequences of a high or low score in terms of resource efficiency are associated with stability and sustainable economic growth. If in the future global prices for raw materials and energy will rise significantly (as most of the tenders and existing research show), countries in the lower tier will face difficulties in comparison with countries with higher efficiency and intensity indicators in order to maintain significantly higher costs and growth rates [5].

Uzbekistan contributed 1.9 billion to the projects of this sector in 2017-2021. Spent a US dollar investment. The total capacity is US \$ 1.1 bn to build solar photovoltaic plants with a total capacity of 500 MW, and 700MM to build 8 GES and 13 small GES. it is planned and implemented to spend dollars. According to research, the energy consumption for an area of 1 square meter in the world is 120-150 kWh per year. In Uzbekistan, 390 kWh of energy is used for an area of the same volume.

Today, several projects for the construction of IES in Uzbekistan have been started. Including: the cost of the UAE company Masdar in the Tomdi District of Navoi region is 600 million. Agreements were made to build a US \$ 500 MW wind farm. When the station was fully commissioned in 2024, it will generate 1.8 billion kWh of electricity per year and 546 million in 1 year. cubic meters of natural gas are saved. Saudi Arabia's ACWA Power has signed an agreement to build 2 IES with a capacity of 1,000 MW with a value of US \$ 1.3 bn in the Ghijduwon and Peshko districts of Bukhara province, with 3.6 bn kWh of electricity delivered annually and 1.1 bn cubic metres of natural gas saved annually when these stations were commissioned in 2023 [6].

Currently, the use of electricity is becoming very expensive. That is, we use electricity 3-4 times more than in other countries. 23% of energy is being lost in the transmission of it to consumers, and 20% of gas resources are being lost in the use of natural gas. The trunk of Energy Transfer is 80% outdated, not in demand. According to experts from the Republican Center for Economic Research, alternative energy sources institutions, 700,000 new jobs will be created on the basis of the use of solar and wind energy, the employment of photoelectronics, one million.. it is said that it is possible to produce tons of biotopliva and 400 thousand tons of artificial biotopliva.

In the national economy, several main problems can be distinguished that hinder the process of implementing the green type of development into life. This is in particular:

- lack of financial resources;
- lack of necessary technologies in the national economy;
- not sufficiently developed legal framework in the field of green technologies;

- unwillingness of traditional sector companies to change themselves business according to the requirements of the green economy;
- lack of qualified specialists;
- the possibility of job loss, especially at the local level, is in the process transition to an environmentally friendly production method;

CONCLUSION

Ensuring the growth of the economy does not put any obstacles to the development of the green economy, but rather the efficient use of resources maintains moderation and ensures continuity. In particular, the rational use of Natural Resources avoids the inappropriate use of the reserve of natural resources by its abuse. The dependence of some countries on Natural Resources is at a high level, and their indicators of economic growth are formed mainly by the consumption of Natural Resources. It is also natural that countries with very wide resource consumption, whose environmental impact is also difficult to ensure sustainable growth for many years.

In conclusion, investments in wind energy, water energy and solar energy in Uzbekistan lead to the fact that the possibility of generating 6 times more electricity than we need for Uzbekistan.

The efficiency of Natural Resources and their use in all respects serves to increase the economic capabilities of the country. But there are several other factors that must be taken into account that carry the economy along the path of continuous development. The use of Natural Capital One of the most basic of the efficiency indicators is the efficient use of energy resources.

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Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 2

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.